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Case-study report on HBM-indicators

Additional Deliverable Report

AD5.3

WP5 Translation of results into policy

Deadline: November 2019

Upload by Coordinator: 13/12/2019

Entity	Name of person responsible	Short name institution	Date [Received]
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2 Glossary

BBzP Benzyl butyl phthalate

cx-MEHP Mono-(2-ethyl-5-carboxypentyl) phthalate

DEHP Di-2-ethylhexyl phthalate

DiBP Diisobutyl phthalate

DiNP Diisononyl phthalate

DnBP Di-n-butyl phthalate

EEA European Environment Agency

ERV European Reference Values

ESB Environmental Specimen Bank

FOSA Perfluorooctylsulfonamide

HBM Human Biomonitoring

HBM4EU Human Biomonitoring Initiative in Europe

HBM-GV Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values

IPCHEM Information Platform for Chemical Monitoring

ISCED International Standard Classification of Education

MBzP Mono benzyl phthalate

MiBP Mono-iso-butyl phthalate

MiNP Mono-iso-nonyl phthalate

MnBP Mono butyl phthalate

N-EtFOSA N-ethylperfluoro-1-octanesulphonamide

N-MeFOSA N-methylperfluoro-1 octanesulphonamide

OH-MEHP Mono-(2-ethyl-5-hydroxy-hexyl)-phthalate

oxo-MEHP Mono-(2-ethyl-5-oxohexyl)-phthalate

PFAS Per- and polyfluorinated compounds

PFBA Perfluoro-n-butanoic acid

PFBS Perfluorobutane sulfonic acid

PFDA perfluoro-n-decanoic acid

PFDoDA Perfluorodecanoic Acid

PFDS Perfluoro-1-decanesulfonate

PFHpA Perfluoro-n-heptanoic acid

PFHxA Perfluoro-n-hexanoic acid

PFHxS Perfluoro-1-hexanesulfonate

PFNA Perfluoro-n-nonanoic acid

PFOA perfluorooctanoic acid

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PFOS perfluorooctane sulfonate

PFPeA perfluoro-n-pentanoic acid

PFTeDA perfluoro-n-tetradecanoic acid

PFTrDA perfluoro-n-tridecanoic acid

PFUnDA perfluoroundecanoic acid

UBA German Environment Agency (Umweltbundesamt)

VITO Flemish Institute for Technological Research (Vlaamse Instelling voor Technologisch Onderzoek)

WP Work package

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3 Abstract/Summary

Under the Human Biomonitoring Initiative in Europe (HBM4EU), we are developing human biomonitoring (HBM) based indicators that can help answer some of the policy questions addressed in the [Scoping documents](#) for each prioritised substance group within the project. Due to the limited number of harmonized datasets in the HBM4EU repository and IPCHEM, it is difficult to derive these indicators for the time being.

Instead, a ‘case study’ approach on building HBM indicators for selected substances such as phthalates, bisphenol A (BPA), per- and polyfluorinated compounds (PFAS) and cadmium (Cd) has been undertaken. These substances were chosen due to their datasets being available in the HBM4EU repository in the internal webpages, and their link to the HBM guidance values (HBM-GV) derived under Task 5.2.

Therefore, an overview of the available aggregated data was collected and the use of the indicators to answer policy questions was elaborated.

However, to achieve the goal to derive quality assured and harmonised indicators, it is imperative that more data owners submit their data to the HBM4EU repository.

4 Introduction

As part of Task 5.4 which deals with the application of HBM-based indicators under WP5 (Translation of results into policy), the European Environment Agency (EEA), the Flemish Institute for Technological Research (Vlaamse Instelling voor Technologisch Onderzoek - VITO) and the German Environment Agency (Umweltbundesamt - UBA) developed a framework for applying the HBM-based indicators and how they can contribute to answer the policy questions derived in the Scoping Documents for each prioritized substance/substance group under HBM4EU.

Indicators are illustrators of data interpretation that bring information in an easy and accessible way to a broader audience be it scientists, policy makers or the general public.

The HBM4EU WP5 indicators are designed to answer key policy questions and support chemical policy making by using HBM data collections. The indicators will include aspects such as policy monitoring, time and spatial trends in internal exposure, internal exposure of vulnerable groups and specific subpopulations. Eventually, they can be compared with indicators based on consumption data, environmental and food datasets, and are aimed at complementing other sets of indicators on human health (WHO) and environment & health (EEA).

According to the strategy and concept that was developed in the first year of the project ([Deliverable 5.3](#), [Buekers et al. 2018](#)), the HBM4EU WP5 indicators are classified as follows:

- ▶ Results indicators
- ▶ Impact indicators

Measurement of the concentration of a substance in blood or urine could be defined as ‘HBM indicator of internal exposure’ and is an example of a result indicator. It does not give information on the hazard of the chemical, at which level an effect will occur (potency) or of the risk of being exposed. Furthermore, HBM data can be compared with a level below which no adverse health effects are expected (for example, the HBM guidance value or HBM-GV). In this case, impact indicators can be developed.

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Initially, the indicators would be developed from the aggregated data available in IPCHEM. As the first datasets became available in IPCHEM, we constructed the first indicators based on the available published information (see [Deliverable 5.3](#)). These included data from a pre-HBM4EU project on human biomonitoring: DEMOCOPHES. As this is still limited, indicators will be developed with data that will become available from the aligned studies (2020) with supporting information from data in IPCHEM and the HBM4EU repository. The aligned studies are the product of an extensive EU wide collection of harmonised HBM data under WP8. The purpose of which is to obtain samples and HBM data across Europe by harmonizing ongoing HBM studies in 21 countries¹.

This deliverable elaborates on how to display and frame these indicators, as well as the quality aspects that are needed for the comparison of datasets. To further strengthen the understanding of the indicators and their interpretation a more detailed elaboration has been undertaken in this additional deliverable to illustrate what data are needed for their calculation and what are the final messages of the indicators. Finally, for each substance/substance group, it is shown how they may help answer the policy questions.

This document focuses only on four substance groups: phthalates, BPA, PFAS and cadmium. As a ‘case-study’, the application of the indicators is shown in more detail for phthalates. For the other substances (Cd, bisphenols, PFAS) an overview of available aggregated data in the repository of HBM4EU is given. As more data becomes available, the same strategy will be applied for the other substances and visualisation of the indicators will be performed.

Indicators developed based on the aggregated data in the repository of HBM4EU, are not included at this stage as the deliverable is public and data from the HBM4EU repository can only be used with permission of the Data Controller or the Data Owner/Data Provider. Furthermore, these indicators are limited to the small number of available datasets that are not yet harmonised.

To produce robust and scientifically proven answers to the policy questions, the indicators need to be provided with harmonised and quality assured data which will become available in the course of the project.

5 Derivation of HBM indicators

Based in the [deliverable 5.3](#) and the conceptual framework derived for developing HBM-based indicators, first steps in how to communicate the indicators have been undertaken. Table 1 contains all the aspects that are needed to derive HBM-based indicators under this task.

In a first step, clear names for the indicators have been developed that are easy to understand. In a next step, the statistical parameters that will be used to illustrate the indicators have been defined. Finally, the mathematical calculation has been elucidated to achieve results that are easy and clear to interpret and may help policy makers in answering the following questions:

- a) Were policy actions to minimise chemical exposure effective?
- b) Are there inequalities regarding internal chemical exposure between different age groups, sexes, people with different socioeconomic status (International Standard Classification of Education - ISCED) or between different countries?

¹ Within the aligned studies, 3 age groups of interest are investigated: children age 6-11, teenagers age 12-19 and adults 20-39 years of age. Within each age group, 10 to 11 different countries will participate. The spread of these countries over the 4 geographical regions of Europe (N, E, S, W) is in proportion to the percentage of inhabitants of those regions. Each country provides 300 samples, with the exception of a few smaller countries who are providing a reduced number of samples. In each age group, exposure to different priority chemicals are analysed. In children: phthalates and DINCH, and flame retardants; in teenagers: phthalates and DINCH, and perfluorinated compounds; and in adults: cadmium, bisphenols and PAHs.

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c) Is the concentration of internal chemical exposure expected to have health consequences?

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Table 1: Overview of indicators that will be derived under T5.4. Statistical analysis is done by WP10 on Data Management and Analysis before the data is used.

Indicator	Parameter	Calculation	Interpretation
Temporal increase or stabilisation of internal exposure possibly related to policy action	Temporal trends of substance (P50 values measured throughout the relevant time period, including first P50 value and the last measured P50 value) related to policy actions/implementation.	<p>increase in substance concentration:</p> $x\% = \left(\frac{\text{Last P50value} - \text{firstP50value}}{\text{first P50 value}} \right) \times 100$	Increase in substance concentration or stable concentration may indicate an emerging chemical or it may indicate that policy actions taken are not effective or not effective enough to cause a (further) decrease.
Possible effectiveness of policy actions in minimizing chemical exposure Eg. Efficiency indicators (Type C): Are we improving? Policy effectiveness indicators (Type D): Are the measures working?	Temporal trends of substance (P50 values measured throughout the relevant time period, including first P50 value and the last measured P50 value in whole time period needed with an absolute minimum of 3 values in the temporal trend) possibly related to policy		
		<p>Decrease of substance concentration:</p> $x\% = \left(\frac{\text{First P50value} - \text{LastP50value}}{\text{firstP50value}} \right) \times 100$	Decrease of substance concentration possibly related with efficient policy actions.

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	actions/implementation		
Inequality of internal chemical exposure	Stratification for different age groups (P50 values used for time trends)	<p>No overlap of 95% confidence interval on mean internal exposure values of different age groups is considered as “differences in exposure”.</p> <p>In future, when high quality data sets will become available through the HBM4EU aligned studies, in-depth statistical testing for significant differences will be performed to find additional differences than those just based on ‘non-overlap’ of 95% confidence intervals of two subpopulations like age groups.</p>	Differences in internal exposure between different age groups exist.
			No indication of differences in exposure between different age groups.
	Stratification for sex (women/men) (P50 values used for time trends)	<p>No overlap of 95% confidence interval between mean internal exposure values of different sexes is considered as “differences in exposures”.</p>	Women are more highly exposed than men.
			Men are more highly exposed than women.
			No indication of sex differences.
	Stratification for ISCED (P50 values used for time trends)	<p>ISCED related “differences in chemical burden of exposure” are based on no overlap of 95% confidence interval.</p>	People with different educational level (based on ISCED) do differ in chemical exposure (educational level is used as a proxy for differences in life style and environment).
No direct/strong indication for correlation between educational level and chemical exposure.			

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	Stratification for countries (P50 values used for time trends)	Statistical significance of country differences in chemical burden of exposure. Link with one of WP10's outcomes on distributions of exposure in different countries. This is only valid when the country's data are representative for the country.	Differences in internal exposure between countries indicated.
			Differences in burden of exposure between countries appear absent.
Health relevance regarding internal chemical exposure	Extent of exceedance: 95 th Percentile in relation to human biomonitoring guidance values (HBM-GV)	$E_{exceedance} = \frac{P95}{HBM\ GV}$	Value > 1: Indicates how far the 95th percentile is above the health-based guidance values. The higher the value above 1, the larger the probability of health impact based on current knowledge. Results can be used in priority setting framework to rank substances for further actions.
			Value < 1: I.e. $E_{exceedance} < 1$. At least 95% of sampled population shows internal exposures below HBM-GV.
	Percentage of exceedance: Individual data of n (number of participants exceeding HBM-GV) and N (total	$P_{exceedance} = \frac{(n > HBM-GV)}{N} \times 100\%$	P > 0 %. A proportional number of participants exceed the HBM-GV. Risk of health impairment for that part of the population cannot be excluded. Results can be used in priority setting framework to rank substances for further actions.

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	number of participants) for each country		<p>P = 0 %. No participants exceed the HBM-GV.</p> <p>There is no anticipated risk of health impairment according to current knowledge.</p>
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Quality aspects of indicators:

It is of value to mention once again, that the goal is to develop indicators based on the data from comparable studies such as the aligned studies, with data currently in IPCHEM and the HBM4EU repository as supporting info. In the aligned studies, with better quality control and single measurement data available, in-depth statistical testing for significant differences will be performed to find additional differences than those just based on 'non-overlap' of 95% confidence intervals of two subpopulations, like age groups, in the "inequality of internal chemical exposure" indicator.

Comparisons between the European countries is challenging due to aspects such as differences in sampling years, differences in selected age groups, differences in the use of validated analytical methods/protocols and quality assurance, differences in matrices collected and differences in measured metabolites. For quality reasons, it is necessary that only comparisons between same years of sampling and similar study groups are made. The landscape of chemicals is continuously changing. If geographical comparisons are made, studies should be selected that have collected samples in the same years. When comparing data, it is necessary to check whether the study groups have a sufficient number of participants (N=120) to guarantee robust and reliable results for the study population that allow comparison with other study populations. To be able to compare data it is necessary to ensure that the respective chemical has been analysed in the same and adequate matrix, such as blood (cord blood, whole blood, plasma, serum), urine (24h-urine, morning urine, spot urine) or hair. This includes the representative metabolite for the parent compound. It is also a requirement that the corresponding analytical method is validated and quality assured.

The indicators task will use the aggregated data that has been revised under WP10.

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6 Framework of indicators for phthalate exposure

Plasticizers are a huge group of chemicals that are used in various consumer products such as food packaging, children's toys, personal care products, pharmaceuticals and many more. Due to their ubiquitous use, burden of exposure to plasticizers, like phthalates, is widespread and their adverse health effects make it an overarching health issue (Heudorf, Mersch-Sundermann, & Angerer, 2007). Experimental studies showed that burden of exposure of phthalates mainly disturb hormonal development of male laboratory animals based on anti-androgenic effects. Especially the exposure to the unborn child in the sensitive time interval (2nd trimester of pregnancy) when the determination of the sex takes place, is of major relevance (Howdeshell, Hotchkiss, & Gray, 2017). Due to the suppression of insulin-like 3 protein (InsL3), phthalate metabolites provoke adverse reproductive and developmental effects. The so called "phthalate syndrome" is described as the occurrence of different health effects such as infertility, decreased sperm count, cryptorchidism (undescended testes), hypospadias (malformation of the penis) and other reproductive tract defects that lead to disorders in male sexual development. There is a group of phthalates described that are proven to provoke phthalate syndrome (Gennings, 2014). The 5 phthalates DEHP, DiNP, DnBP, DiBP and BBzP will be used as an indicator for phthalate exposure regarding population health to phthalate syndrome. Within HBM4EU, these substances are on the first list of priority substances and grouped under Category A since HBM data is available for at least one country from one of the four geographical regions of the European Union defined by the UN. For all these substances well-established analytical methods exist, sufficient HBM data are available and all substances are regulated under REACH. All of them, except DiNP, are classified as toxic for reproduction 1B under Annex VI to the Classification Labelling and Packaging (CLP) regulation (EC 1272/2008). In addition to their reprotoxic properties, DEHP, DnBP, DiBP and BBzP also have endocrine disrupting properties and have been classified as substances of very high concern (Annex XIV EC 1907/2006) and therefore included in the candidate list for the inclusion in Annex XIV of the REACH regulation (Annex XIV of REACH EC 1907/2006).

To assess the exposure to phthalates, four indicators can be developed based on our concept:

- 1) *Temporal increase or stable internal exposure*: This could indicate whether there is an emerging chemical (concentrations going up) or whether body burden remains stable.
- 2) *Effectiveness of policy actions in minimizing chemical exposure*: Temporal trends will show if exposure for the group of phthalates is decreasing. They could also indicate that risk management has been effective, for cases in which the stabilisation or the decrease has been started at the time of implementation of a policy action. Time trends and the increase or decrease will be calculated for each individual phthalate of the group and a general time trend for the group will be summarized. As these phthalates are banned or restricted for use since 2015 under Annex XIV/XVII, they need to be considered together and a time trend for the whole group may show exposure from the group of phthalates causing phthalate syndrome.
- 3) *Inequality of chemical exposure*: Differences in exposure between different age groups, sexes (women and men), educational level (ISCED) for each individual phthalate of the group, and country differences will be evaluated.
- 4) *Health relevance regarding internal chemical exposure*: Comparisons of exposure for each individual phthalate of the group, will show if HBM-GV are exceeded or not. If possible, a general conclusion for the whole group of phthalates causing phthalate syndrome will be made.

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The visualisation of the indicators will be done when harmonised and comparable data are available. This will be due to 2020 when the aligned studies under WP8 have been finalised and more data has been transferred to the HBM4EU repository and IPCHEM.

6.1 Quality aspects for indicator derivation of phthalates

Indicators summarize complex scientific data into simple and clear messages, and quality control of the respective data is a prerequisite. For quality reasons, it is necessary that only comparisons between same years of sampling and same study group are made. It is also a requirement that the same and the adequate matrices are being selected and that the corresponding analytical method is validated and quality assured. This includes the representative metabolite for the parent compound. Detailed information about these quality aspects are discussed in the following section.

6.1.1 Years of sampling

The landscape of chemicals is continuously changing. Therefore, it is relevant to compare data that has been collected at the same years of sampling (excluding time trend analysis). If not, differences in exposure between countries will most likely be based in differences between the years.

Phthalate data in the HBM4EU repository comprises studies from 2006-2016. It is therefore suggested to only compare studies with the same years of sampling.

6.1.2 Study group

When comparing data, it is necessary to check whether the study groups have a sufficient number of participants (N=120) to guarantee robust and reliable results for the study population that allow comparison with other study populations, that the respective chemical has been analysed in the same matrix and that the analytical method is validated and quality assured. These aspects need to be considered when using data for constructing the indicators.

For the selected group of phthalates, the number of participants of the respective studies range between 51 and 913 (status of September 2019 of HBM4EU repository). Those variabilities in study size lead to differences in accuracy of the study results and need to be communicated for the interpretation of the indicator results.

Stratification for age groups are possible for phthalates regarding children (3-5 years old, 6-11 years old), teenagers (12-19 years old) and adults (20-39 years old, 40-59 years old). Stratification for sex can be made in eight HBM studies (DEMOCOPHES, Czech Human Biomonitoring Children's exposure, Copenhagen Mother-Child cohort, Copenhagen Puberty Study, PCB cohort Slovakia, Flemish Environment and Health Study 2 Reference Adolescents, Flemish Environment and Health Study 2 Reference Adults, Flemish Environment and Health Study 3 Reference Adolescents). Stratification for ISCED can be made for four HBM studies (DEMOCOPHES, Czech Human Biomonitoring Children's exposure, Flemish Environment and Health Study 2 Reference Adolescents, Flemish Environment, Flemish Environment and Health Study 3 Reference Adolescents). Comparisons between countries is currently only possible for DEMOCOPHES data, as the data are harmonised and quality assured. However, in this comparison the data are not fully representative of the countries as they were only collected in two sampling sites per country (rural and urban site).

6.1.3 Matrix

To be able to compare data it is necessary to ensure that the respective chemical has been analysed in the same matrix, such as blood (cord blood, whole blood, plasma), urine (24h-urine, morning urine, spot urine) or hair.

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Phthalates are acute acting chemicals which do not circulate over a long time in the human body, as they are rapidly excreted over urine. Experimental studies showed that around 50 % of the DEHP and DiNP metabolites are excreted after 24 and 48 hours in urine after a single oral dose (H. M. Koch & Angerer, 2007; H. M. Koch, Bolt, Preuss, & Angerer, 2005). Based on this rapid urinary excretion of phthalates a single urine sample represents only recent exposure. It must be considered that the assessment of spot and morning urine samples may lead to an over- or underestimation of internal exposure regarding intra-individual variation over the day. Dilution of the urine has also an effect on the concentrations of phthalates. Therefore 24h-urine samples are discussed as the matrix of first choice and will be preferred for the use of indicators.

As the efforts are higher to collect 24h-urine samples not all the datasets have this matrix available. So far, only one dataset from the German ESB is available in the HBM4EU repository (Holger M. Koch et al., 2017). Therefore, morning urine or spot urine will be used as the matrix of second choice. It was shown for some phthalates that in relation to 24h-urine best comparability can be taken from morning urine samples (Frederiksen et al., 2013). For phthalates there are six HBM studies available in the repository that collected morning urine samples (see in the overview Table 2). Spot urine can be collected at different time points per day and is therefore less comparable. Six HBM studies that collected spot urine samples are available in the repository for their chemical analysis of the selected phthalates.

6.1.4 Phthalate metabolites

For assessing burden of exposure from phthalates or any other chemical compound it is necessary that the adequate metabolite is reflecting the exposure from the parent compound (relevant exposure biomarker, i.e. if the metabolite is specific to reflect exposure from the parent compound). The fraction of urinary excretion (FUE) for that exposure biomarker indicates which proportion of the total daily exposure is excreted through urine.

When phthalates enter the human body, they undergo a series of phase I hydrolysis and phase II conjugation reactions resulting in different metabolites. These are subsequently excreted in faeces and urine (Frederiksen, Skakkebaek, & Andersson, 2007). For the derivation of HBM-GV, the definition of a relevant metabolite or a combination of metabolites is crucial. This can also potentially include the parent compound itself as there is a qualitative aspect in the HBM-GV (what analyte(s)) and a quantitative aspect expressed as blood or for phthalates, a urinary (combination of) concentrations.

In HBM4EU, this will be based on information regarding toxicokinetics including rate(s) of excretion of metabolite(s) collected under Task 5.2 (responsible for the development of HBM-GV). Based on hazard identification and exposure/dose-response information, HBM-GV are being derived. The HBM-GV indicate the internal exposure (blood concentrations) or related urinary excretion levels below which adverse health effects are not expected. An exceedance of the so-called benchmark levels indicates if the exposure is a potential health concern and helps to set further priorities between different chemicals.

In the course of this work, T5.2 is also assessing the specific metabolites from the parent compound that are relevant to reflect exposure. These selected metabolites will also be used for the elaboration of the indicators. A summary of the phthalates, their selected metabolites and the corresponding HBM-GV derived under HBM4EU WP5.2 is given in Table 2.

Table 2: Overview of the group of phthalates and their defined metabolites for derivation of HBM-GV.

Parent compound	Metabolite	HBM-GV derived in WP5.2
DEHP	oxo-MEHP and OH-MEHP	\sum [5oxo-MEHP and 5OH-MEHP] in urine:

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	or cx-MEHP and OH-MEHP	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - children (6-13y): 340 µg/L - adults: 500 µg/L <p>∑[5cx-MEHP and 5OH-MEHP] in urine:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - children (6-13y): 380 µg/L - adults: 570 µg/L <p>(for more information see D5.2)</p>
DiBP	MiBP	n.a.; Derivation of HBM-GV will be published by end of the year in D5.6
DiNP	MiNP	n.a.; Derivation of HBM-GV not planned
BBzP	MBzP	n.a.; Derivation of HBM-GV will be published by end of the year in D5.6
DnBP	MnBP	n.a.; Derivation of HBM-GV will be published by end of the year in D5.6

7 Overview of available data within HBM4EU repository

Currently, only a limited number of datasets with aggregated data are available in the HBM4EU repository that hamper the derivation of robust indicators.

Comparisons between the European countries is challenging due to aspects such as sampling years, differences in selected age groups, differences in the use of validated analytical methods/protocols and quality assurance, differences in matrices collected and differences in measured metabolites. All these quality aspects were discussed in detail in chapter 6.1. Therefore, only an overview of the available datasets for each substance group will be given and further visualisation of the indicators will be done in the remaining 2 years of the project.

7.1 Phthalates

Table 3: Overview of the selected phthalates and their available aggregated data in the HBM4EU repository (status in September 2019).

Phthalate	Country	Study	Sampling years	Matrix	Stratification
DEHP	Austria	EAA Phthalates and BPA in Austrian general pop (PBAT)	2010-2012	Spot urine ²	Age groups Sex
	Czechia	Czech HBM Children's exposure (HBM-CE)	2016-2017	Morning urine ³	Age groups Sex IESCED (medium/high)
		DEMOCOPHES	2011-2012	Morning urine	Age groups Sex ISCED (medium/high)
	Denmark	Copenhagen Mother Child Cohort (CPH-MC)	2006-2007	Spot urine	Age groups Sex
		Copenhagen Puberty Study (CPHPUB) cross-sectional study	2006-2008	Morning urine	Age groups Sex
		Danish Young Man Study (DYMS)	2007-2009	Spot urine	Time trend 2007-2009

² A spot urine sample is based on one single urine void,

³ A morning urine sample is a specific spot sample, i.e. taken at a fixed and specific time point, i.e. the first morning void.

		Odense Child Cohort	2010-2013	Spot urine	Pregnant women
	Hungary	DEMOCOPHES	2011-2012	Morning urine	Age groups Sex ISCED (medium/high)
	Spain	DEMOCOPHES	2011-2012	Morning urine	Age groups Sex
	Slovenia	DEMOCOPHES	2011-2012	Morning urine	Age groups Sex
	Slovakia	DEMOCOPHES	2011-2012	Morning urine	Age groups Sex ISCED (medium/high)
		UKF-Children cohort	2015-2016	Spot urine	Toddlers/Children 1-11y
		UKF-mother newborn cohort	2014-2015	Morning urine	Pregnant women
		SZU-PCBcohort	2014-2017	Morning urine	Teenagers 12-19y Sex
	Belgium	DEMOCOPHES	2011-2012	Morning urine	Age groups Sex
		FLEHS II - Adolescents - Reference	2008-2009	Morning urine	Age groups Sex ISCED (medium/high)
		FLEHS III - Adolescents Reference	2013	Spot urine	Teenagers 12-19 and different age groups of mothers at birth Sex ISCED (medium/high)
	Germany	UBA Environmental Specimen Bank (ESB)	2007-2015	24h-urine	Time trend Sex
BBzP	Austria	EAA Phthalates and BPA in	2010-2012	Spot urine	Age groups

		Austrian general pop (PBAT)			Sex
	Czechia	Czech HBM Children's exposure (HBM-CE)	2016-2017	Morning urine	Age groups Sex ISCED (medium/high)
		DEMOCOPHES	2011-2012	Morning urine	Age groups Sex ISCED (medium/high)
	Denmark	Copenhagen Mother Child Cohort (CPH-MC)	2006-2007	Spot urine	Age groups Sex
		Copenhagen Puberty Study (CPHPUB) cross-sectional study	2006-2008	Morning urine	Age groups Sex
		Danish Young Man Study (DYMS)	2007-2009	Spot urine	Time trend 2007-2009
		Odense Child Cohort	2010-2013	Spot urine	Pregnant women
	Hungary	DEMOCOPHES	2011-2012	Morning urine	Age groups Sex ISCED (medium/high)
	Spain	DEMOCOPHES	2011-2012	Morning urine	Age groups Sex
	Slovenia	DEMOCOPHES	2011-2012	Morning urine	Age groups Sex
	Slovakia	DEMOCOPHES	2011-2012	Morning urine	Age groups Sex ISCED (medium/high)
		UKF-Children cohort	2015-2016	Spot urine	Toddlers/Children 1-11y
	Belgium	DEMOCOPHES	2011-2012	Morning urine	Age groups Sex

		FLEHS II - Adolescents - Reference	2008-2009	Morning urine	Age groups Sex ISCED (medium/high)
		FLEHS III - Adolescents Reference	2013	Spot urine	Teenagers 12-19 and different age groups of mothers at birth Sex ISCED (medium/high)
	Germany	UBA Environmental Specimen Bank (ESB)	2007-2015	24h-urine	Time trend Sex
DIBP	Austria	EAA Phthalates and BPA in Austrian general pop (PBAT)	2010-2012	Spot urine	Age groups Sex
	Czechia	Czech HBM Children's exposure (HBM-CE)	2016-2017	Morning urine	Age groups Sex ISCED (medium/high)
		DEMOCOPHES	2011-2012	Morning urine	Age groups Sex ISCED (medium/high)
	Denmark	Copenhagen Puberty Study (CPHPUB) cross-sectional study	2006-2008	Morning urine	Age groups Sex
		Danish Young Man Study (DYMS)	2007-2009	Spot urine	Time trend 2007-2009
		Odense Child Cohort	2010-2013	Spot urine	Pregnant women
	Slovakia	SZU-PCBcohort	2014-2017	Morning urine	Teenagers 12-19y Sex
		UKF-Children cohort	2015-2016	Spot urine	Toddlers/Children 1-11y

	Belgium	FLEHS III - Adolescents Reference	2013	Spot urine	Teenagers 12-19 and different age groups of mothers at birth Sex ISCED (medium/high)
	Germany	UBA Environmental Specimen Bank (ESB)	2007-2015	24h-urine	Time trend Sex
DnBP	Austria	EAA Phthalates and BPA in Austrian general pop (PBAT)	2010-2012	Spot urine	Age groups Sex
	Czechia	Czech HBM Children's exposure (HBM-CE)	2016-2017	Morning urine	Age groups Sex ISCED (medium/high)
	Denmark	Copenhagen Puberty Study (CPHPUB) cross-sectional study	2006-2008	Morning urine	Age groups Sex
		Danish Young Man Study (DYMS)	2007-2009	Spot urine	Time trend 2007-2009
		Odense Child Cohort	2010-2013	Spot urine	Pregnant women
	Slovakia	SZU-PCBcohort	2014-2017	Morning urine	Teenagers 12-19y Sex
		UKF-Children cohort	2015-2016	Spot urine	Toddlers/Children 1-11y
	Belgium	FLEHS II - Adolescents - Reference	2008-2009	Morning urine	Age groups Sex ISCED (medium/high)
		FLEHS III - Adolescents Reference	2013	Spot urine	Teenagers 12-19 and different age groups of mothers at birth Sex

					ISCED (medium/high)
	Germany	UBA Environmental Specimen Bank (ESB)	2007-2015	24h-urine	Time trend Sex
DINP	Denmark	Copenhagen Mother Child Cohort (CPH-MC)	2006-2007	Spot urine	Age groups Sex
		Copenhagen Puberty Study (CPHPUB) cross- sectional study	2006-2008	Morning urine	Age groups Sex
		Danish Young Man Study (DYMS)	2007-2009	Spot urine	Time trend 2007- 2009
		Odense Child Cohort	2010-2013	Spot urine	Pregnant women
		DEMOCOPHES	2011-2012	Morning urine	Age groups Sex
	Slovakia	UKF-Children cohort	2015-2016	Spot urine	Toddlers/Children 1-11y
	Germany	DEMOCOPHES	2011-2012	Morning urine	Age groups Sex
		UBA Environmental Specimen Bank (ESB)	2007-2015	24h-urine	Time trend Sex

7.2 Bisphenols

The following table (Table 4) gives an overview of the aggregated data on BPA that are available in the HBM4EU repository. There are no data available on other bisphenols. BPA includes total BPA

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(free + glucuronide). All samples were spot urine samples except the data of the Environmental Specimen Bank (ESB) (24h-urine in German students).

Table 4 Overview of the available datasets with aggregated data on bisphenol A in the HBM4EU repository (status in September 2019)

Data collection name	Country	Sampling year	Age	Sex	Remark
DYMS	Denmark	2008-2009	18-29	M	Spot urine
OCC	Denmark	2010-2013	18-39	F	Mothers; spot urine
FLEHSIII	Belgium	2014 onwards	>40	M+F	Spot urine
ESB	Germany	2007-2009	20-29	M+F	24h-urine

7.3 PFAS

Similarly to what was done for the previous two substances/groups (phthalates and BPA), an overview of the aggregated data on per- and polyfluorinated substances (PFAS) available in the HBM4EU repository is given below (

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Table 5). The available datasets on PFAS include aggregate data on exposure biomarker levels for perfluorooctylsulfonamide (FOSA), N-ethylperfluoro-1-octanesulphonamide (N-EtFOSA), N-methylperfluoro-1 octanesulphonamide (N-MeFOSA), perfluoro-n-butanoic acid (PFBA), perfluorobutane sulfonic acid (PFBS), perfluoro-n-decanoic acid (PFDA), perfluorodecanoic Acid (PFDoDA), perfluoro-1-decanesulfonate (PFDS), perfluoro-n-heptanoic acid (PFHpA), perfluoro-n-hexanoic acid (PFHxA), perfluoro-1-hexanesulfonate (PFHxS), perfluoro-n-nonanoic acid (PFNA), perfluorooctanoic acid (PFOA), perfluorooctane sulfonate (PFOS), perfluoro-n-pentanoic acid (PFPeA), perfluoro-n-tetradecanoic acid (PFTeDA) and/or perfluoro-n-tridecanoic acid (PFTTrDA) and/or perfluoroundecanoic acid (PFUnDA).

Samples included matrices such as serum, cord- serum and breast milk.

Datasets belonging to Belgium, Czechia, Slovakia and Denmark were collected between (exclusive of last year in the range) 2000–2005, 2005–2010, 2010–2014, and in 2014 and 2017.

The stratifications include information on sex, age groups (including infants under 1-year-old), ISCED, current non-smokers and current non-smokers vs smokers.

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Table 5 Overview of the available datasets with aggregated data on PFAS in the HBM4EU repository (status in September 2019) (*exclusive of that year)

PFAS	Country	Study	Sampling years	Matrix	Stratification
FOSA	Slovakia	SZU_PRENATAL_integration	2010 – 2014*	Breast milk (microg/L) Cord -serum (microg/L)	Sex Age group: Infants < 1 year old, adults ISCED Smokers vs non-smokers
N-EtFOSA	Slovakia	SZU_PRENATAL_integration	2010 – 2014*	Breast milk (microg/L) Cord -serum (microg/L)	Sex Age group: Infants < 1 year old, adults ISCED Smokers vs non-smokers
N-MeFOSA	Slovakia	SZU_PRENATAL_integration	2010 – 2014*	Breast milk (microg/L) Cord blood-serum (microg/L)	Sex Age group: Infants < 1 year old, adults ISCED Smokers vs non-smokers
PFBA	Slovakia	SZU_PRENATAL_integration	2010 – 2014*	Breast milk (microg/L) Cord blood-serum (microg/L)	Sex Age group: Infants < 1 year old, adults ISCED Smokers vs non-smokers
PFBS	Slovakia	SZU_PRENATAL_integration	2010 – 2014*	Breast milk (microg/L)	Females Same age group

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	Belgium	VITO_FLEHS3RefAdult_integration	2014	Blood Serum (microg/L)	Sex Age group ISCED Smokers vs non-smokers
		VITO_FLEHS3RefNb_integration	2010 – 2014* 2014	Cord -plasma (microg/L)	Sex Age group: Infants < 1 year old, adults ISCED Current non-smokers
PFDA	Denmark	SDU_OCC_integration	2010 – 2014*	Serum	Sample at gestational week 10
	Slovakia	SZU_PRENATAL_integration		Breast milk (microg/L) Cord blood-serum (microg/L)	Sex Age group Infants < 1 year old ISCED Smokers vs non-smokers
PFDoDA	Slovakia	SZU_PRENATAL_integration	2010 – 2014*	Breast milk (microg/L) Cord blood-serum (microg/L)	Sex Age group: Infants < 1 year old, adults ISCED Smokers vs non-smokers
PFDS	Slovakia	SZU_PRENATAL_integration	2010 – 2014*	Breast milk (microg/L) Cord blood-serum (microg/L)	Sex Age group: Infants < 1 year old, adults ISCED Smokers vs non-smokers

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PFHpA	Slovakia	SZU_PRENATAL_integration	2010 – 2014*	Breast milk (microg/L) Cord blood-serum (microg/L)	Sex Age group: Infants < 1 year old, adults ISCED Smokers vs non-smokers
PFHxA	Slovakia	SZU_PRENATAL_integration	2010 – 2014*	Breast milk (microg/L) Cord blood-serum (microg/L)	Sex Age group: Infants < 1 year old, adults ISCED Smokers vs non-smokers
PFHxS	Denmark	SDU_OCC_integration	2010 – 2014*	Serum	Sample at gestational week 10
	Slovakia	SZU_PRENATAL_integration	2010 – 2014*	Breast milk (microg/L) Cord blood-serum (microg/L)	Sex Age group: Infants < 1 year old, adults ISCED Smokers vs non-smokers
	Belgium	VITO_FLEHS3RefAdult_integration	2014	Breast milk (microg/L)	Sex Age group ISCED Smokers vs non-smokers
		VITO_FLEHS3RefNb_integration	2010 – 2014* and 2014	Cord blood-plasma (microg/L)	Sex Age of mother Infants < 1 year old ISCED Current non-smokers

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PFNA	Czechia	NIPHPrague_CzechHBM-HM_integration	2017	Breast milk (microg/L)	Women Age 20 - 39 years old ISCED Smokers vs non-smokers
	Denmark	SDU_OCC_integration	2010 – 2014*	Serum	Sample at gestational week 10
	Slovakia	SZU_PRENATAL_integration	2010 – 2014*	Breast milk (microg/L) Cord blood-serum (microg/L)	Sex Age group: Infants < 1 year old, adults ISCED Smokers vs non-smokers
	Belgium	VITO_FLEHS3RefAdult_integration	2014	Blood Serum (microg/L)	Sex Age group ISCED Smokers vs non-smokers
		VITO_FLEHS3RefAdult_integration	2010 – 2014* and 2014	Cord blood-plasma (microg/L)	Sex Age group: Infants < 1 year old, adults ISCED Current non-smokers
PFOA	Czechia	NIPHPrague_CzechHBM-HM_integration	2017	Breast milk (microg/L)	Women Age 20 - 39 years old ISCED Smokers vs non-smokers
	Denmark	SDU_OCC_integration	2010 – 2014*	Serum	Sampling at gestational week 10
	Slovakia	SZU_PCBcohort_integration	2000 – 2005*	Breast milk (microg/L)	Women Age 20 - 39 years old ISCED

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		SZU_PRENATAL_integration	2010 – 2014*	Breast milk (microg/L) Cord blood-serum (microg/L)	Sex Age group: Infants < 1 year old, adults ISCED Smokers vs non-smokers
	Belgium	VITO_FLEHS2HotspotM_integration	2010 – 2014*	Blood Serum (microg/L)	Women Age ISCED Smokers vs non-smokers
		VITO_FLEHS2RefAdult_integration	2005 – 2010*	Blood Serum (microg/L)	Women Age ISCED Smokers vs non-smokers
		VITO_FLEHS2RefNb_integration	2005 – 2010*	Cord blood-plasma (microg/L)	Sex Age ISCED
		VITO_FLEHS3RefAdult_integration	2014	Blood Serum (microg/L)	Sex Age ISCED Smokers vs non-smokers
		VITO_FLEHS3RefNb_integration	2010 – 2014* and 2014	Cord blood-plasma (microg/L)	Sex Age group: Infants < 1 year old, adults ISCED Non-smokers

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PFPeA	Slovakia	SZU_PRENATAL_integration	2010 – 2014*	Breast milk (microg/L) Cord blood-serum (microg/L)	Sex Age group: Infants < 1 year old, adults ISCED Smokers vs non-smokers
PFTeDA	Slovakia	SZU_PRENATAL_integration	2010 – 2014*	Breast milk (microg/L) Cord blood-serum (microg/L)	Sex Age group: Infants < 1 year old, adults ISCED Smokers vs non-smokers
PFTrDA	Slovakia	SZU_PRENATAL_integration	2010 – 2014*	Breast milk (microg/L) Cord blood-serum (microg/L)	Sex Age group: Infants < 1 year old, adults ISCED Smokers vs non-smokers
PFUnDA	Slovakia	SZU_PRENATAL_integration	2010 – 2014*	Breast milk (microg/L) Cord blood-serum (microg/L)	Sex Age group: Infants < 1 year old, adults ISCED Smokers vs non-smokers

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7.4 Cadmium

7.4.1 Urinary cadmium

The following table (Table 6) gives an overview of urinary cadmium aggregated data in the HBM4EU repository. All campaigns collected morning urine samples except in FLEHS I and III where spot urine samples were collected randomly over the day. Urine cadmium reflects integrated exposure over time and total body burden whereas blood cadmium indicates recent exposure.

Table 6 Overview of the available datasets with aggregated data on urinary cadmium in the HBM4EU repository (status in September 2019)

Data collection name	Country	Sampling year	Age	Sex	Remark
NIPH-CZ_CzechHBM-CE_integration	Czechia	2014 onwards	3-11	M+F	
DEMOCOPHES-HU_integration	Hungary	2010-2014	20-59	F	Mothers
DEMOCOPHES-HU_integration	Hungary	2010-2014	6-11	M+F	Children
ISCIII_DEMOCOPHES-SPAIN_integration	Spain	2010-2014	20-59	F	Mothers
ISCIII_DEMOCOPHES-SPAIN_integration	Spain	2010-2014	6-11	M+F	Children
JSI_SLO-DEMOCOPHES_integration	Slovenia	2010-2014	20-59	F	Mothers
JSI_SLO-DEMOCOPHES_integration	Slovenia	2010-2014	6-11	M+F	Children
LSMU_BCAS1_integration	Lithuania	2005-2010	12 to >60	F	Case-control study. Controls.
LSMU_BCAS2_integration	Lithuania	2005-2014	12 to >60	F	Case-control study. Controls.
NIPH-CZ_DEMOCOPHES-CZ_integration	Czechia	2010-2014	20-59	F	Mothers
NIPH-CZ_DEMOCOPHES-CZ_integration	Czechia	2010-2014	6-11	M+F	Children
UVZ_DEMO_HBM4EUData_integration	Slovakia	2010-2014	20-59	F	Mothers

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Data collection name	Country	Sampling year	Age	Sex	Remark
UVZ_DEMO_HBM4EUData_integration	Slovakia	2010-2014	6-11	M+F	Children
VITO_DEMOCOPHES_BE_integration	Belgium	2010-2014	20-59	F	Mothers
VITO_DEMOCOPHES_BE_integration	Belgium	2010-2014	6-11	M+F	Children
VITO_FLEHS1RefAdo_integration	Belgium	2000-2005	12-19	M+F	Spot urine
VITO_FLEHS1RefAdult_integration	Belgium	2000-2005	>40	M+F	Spot urine
VITO_FLEHS2RefAdo_integration	Belgium	2005-2010	12-19	M+F	
VITO_FLEHS2RefAdult_integration	Belgium	2005-2010	20-59	M+F	
VITO_FLEHS3RefAdult_integration	Belgium	2010-2014	>40	M+F	Spot urine

7.4.2 Whole blood cadmium

The following table (Table 7) is an overview of the aggregated data on cadmium in whole blood present in HBM4EU repository.

Table 7 Overview of the available datasets in whole blood with aggregated data for cadmium present in the HBM4EU repository (status in September 2019)

Data collection name	Country	Sampling year	Age	Sex	Remark
NIPH-CZ_CzechHBM-CE_integration	Czechia	2014 onwards	3-11	M+F	

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VITO_FLEHS1RefAdo_integration	Belgium	2000-2005	12-19	M+F	
VITO_FLEHS1RefAdult_integration	Belgium	2000-2005	>40	M+F	
VITO_FLEHS2RefAdo_integration	Belgium	2005-2010	12-19	M+F	
VITO_FLEHS2RefNb_integration	Belgium	2005-2010	Mostly >20	F	Mothers
VITO_FLEHS3RefAdo_integration	Belgium	2010-2014	12-19	M+F	

7.4.3 Cord blood cadmium

The last table with the information present in the HBM4EU repository, provides an overview of aggregated data on cadmium in cord blood.

Table 8 Overview of the available datasets in cord-blood with aggregated data for cadmium present in the HBM4EU repository (status in September 2019)

Data collection name	Country	Sampling year
SZU_PRENATAL_integration	Slovakia	2010-2014
VITO_FLEHS1RefNb_integration	Belgium	2000-2005
VITO_FLEHS2RefNb_integration	Belgium	2005-2010

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VITO_FLEHS3RefNb_integration	Belgium	2010-2014
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8 How indicators can help answer policy questions

Indicators that will be generated with aggregated data available from HBM4EU repository are valuable to display how HBM data can be used to address policy questions.

In this report, each set of policy questions was evaluated against the data that is available in the HBM4EU repository and specific indicators are suggested that will help answer the policy questions.

The indicators generated with HBM data will not be able to help answer all the policy questions, hence only the policy questions for which the indicators may contribute to will be shown in the tables in the following sections.

For the complete list of the policy questions, please refer to the substance webpages of each substance which are available in the [HBM4EU website](#).

8.1 Phthalates

Table 9 Relevant policy questions on phthalates that indicators can contribute to and how.

Policy question	Comment
What is the extent of the current exposure of the EU population to phthalates (Cat A)?	HBM based result indicators can provide information that may answer this question. Data will be used from the HBM4EU repository and later IPCHEM. If enough data become available this indicator will be constructed.
Do the exposure levels differ significantly between the countries?	This indicator illustrates inequalities of internal exposure between the countries and can be constructed if more harmonised HBM data becomes available.
What are the main sources of exposure and the reasons for differences in exposure to phthalates?	This can be illustrated by displaying different indicator sources in IPCHEM based on consumption data, environmental data and HBM data. However, such associations should be interpreted carefully as causality differs from coincidence.
Are there different time trends for unregulated and regulated phthalates? (Starting with Cat. A substances)	This can be illustrated by result indicators using time trends but currently in the HBM4EU repository available datasets are limited by time and countries and no comparisons can be made yet.
How effective have the different mitigation steps and regulations been for phthalates?	This can be shown by result indicators illustrating effectiveness of policy actions based on time trends and calculating gradients of decrease/increase. By indicating the time pattern of mitigation steps next to the time trend line for HBM data, the efficacy of mitigation steps may be highlighted.
Was the introduction of the Authorisation obligation under REACH effective enough to protect the health of European citizens? Is there	This can be illustrated by displaying impact indicators that refer to measured HBM levels in the population to HBM guidance values and hence provide information

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a sufficient decrease of the regulated Cat. A substance levels (P95) in the population (general/children?) from year 2007 until today with focus on health relevance?	on whether or not the internal exposure has a health relevance, or if authorisation efforts are being successful. This will be done when harmonised and comparable data are available in the HBM4EU repository.
What are the high exposure groups?	If HBM data can be stratified according to e.g. age, sex, ISCED, geography, the result indicators can display differences in exposure among different subgroups. WP10 will collect aggregated and stratified data that can be used to display this indicator.
Is the exposure to phthalates of health relevance for the general population and vulnerable groups (inter alia children and pregnant women? What part of the population has exposure levels exceeding the HBM guidance values - if existing)?	This can be displayed using impact indicators illustrating health relevance regarding internal exposure by relating HBM levels in the specified subgroups to derived HBM-GVs elaborated under T5.2. This will be done when harmonised and comparable data are available within HBM4EU repository.
Does the health relevance depend on age, sex and socio-economic status?	See above. Stratification for age, sex and ISCED needed. This will be done when harmonised and comparable data are available in HBM4EU repository/IPCHEM.
Are there knowledge gaps and related research needs for phthalates?	If the applied indicators show new findings in social inequalities or trends of internal exposure, this may help to address new research questions, knowledge gaps and feed into the policy making process when advice is necessary (e.g. category changes in certain phthalates?)

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8.2 Bisphenols

There are several critical questions concerning bisphenols that need to be addressed. These and the policy questions are based on, (see Table 10 with the relevant policy questions below) were copied from the 17 January 2018 version 4.0 of the Scoping Document for [Bisphenol A](#).

1. Whether different regulations in different countries lead to different internal exposure values and whether the increasingly frequent use of substitutes has led to increased exposure of substitutes and to the presence of mixtures of bisphenols in humans.
2. Identify safety values taking into consideration the accumulating knowledge on Bisphenol toxicity particularly at low doses.
3. Whether substitutes are safer than BPA considering their hazardous properties and current and expected exposure to those compounds

Table 10 Relevant policy questions on bisphenols that indicators can contribute to and how.

Policy question	Comment
1. What is the current exposure of the EU population to BPA?	HBM based result indicators can provide information that is relevant for this question. In IPCHEM/repository, there is not enough data available to answer this now.
2. Do different regulatory controls across the EU concerning in particular BPA lead to different exposures?	Can only be answered once multi-year data (temporal data) will become available. Displaying HBM time data trends next to legislative measured from different countries may inform policy makers.
3. Are bisphenols (BPA and substitutes) exposure levels of concern for health?	Impact indicators can be used to illustrate this as they relate measured levels to HBM-GV.
4. Is occupational exposure of cashiers a health concern?	Specific data collections of BPA levels in cashiers need to be presented in relation to HBM-GV (impact indicator). Soon as this information becomes available the indicator can be constructed. Specific occupational (cashier) HBM data need to be made available (literature search).
6. Are health risks age and sex dependent?	HBM data can be stratified according to e.g. age, sex. These datasets can be related to HBM-GVs. WP10 is collecting aggregated stratified datasets that can be used to display this indicator.
8. How can HBM feed into assessment of the Tolerable Daily Intake (TDI) for BPA, as set by the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA)?	We can contribute through the use of impact indicators that relate the measured HBM levels to HBM-GVs. This indicator should be less than one if external intake levels comply with the TDI.

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8.3 PFAS

Table 11: Relevant policy questions on PFAS that indicators can contribute to and how.

Policy Questions	Comment
1. What is the current exposure of the EU population to PFASs and do they exceed Guidance values (reference and HBM values), where available?	Impact indicators can be constructed to provide the information. The HBM levels are referred to HBM-GVs. This can be performed with EU-wide RV HBM values and with country specific HBM data. More data are needed and further exchange with T5.2 (Derivation of HBM-GV) envisaged.
2. Are there differences in exposure of the EU population to regulated and non-regulated PFAS?	Result indicators that display HBM levels for regulated and not yet regulated PFAS can be displayed if enough data become available in HBM4EU repository/IPCHEM.
3. Has restriction of PFOS according to the POP Regulation led to a reduction in exposure, especially for children?	An indicator can be displayed based on aggregated HBM data stratified for children, and time trends may illustrate success or failure in reduction.
4. Is exposure driven by diet, consumer exposure, occupation or environmental contamination?	IPCHEM contains substance specific data in food items, consumption data and environmental data. These can be displayed next to the specific HBM data, preferentially at the same aggregation level. The data will have to be checked for harmonisation and compliance with the quality criteria, before a potential indicator on the route of exposure is done.
5. Which areas and environmental media in Europe are contaminated with PFAS?	This cannot directly be answered but result indicators for regional HBM data can inform about geographical exposures.
6. Can differences in PFAS profiles be observed in different population groups and time periods?	Result indicators can be constructed to display geographical differences and time trends using HBM levels. This will be done when harmonised and comparable data are available within HBM4EU repository/IPCHEM.
7. What are the PFAS levels and health effects in vulnerable population groups?	As aggregated HBM data are being collected stratified for sex, age, geography and ISCED, they may inform about highly exposed subpopulations and the levels in vulnerable populations.

8.4 Cadmium

For cadmium, there are 4 policy questions present in the scoping document (available [here](#)):

1. Is there a link between high soil contamination with Cd and human exposure via dietary sources?
2. Are environmental quality standards for Cd in water sufficiently restrictive to protect human health from exposure to Cd via the environment and via dietary sources?
3. What is the maximum acceptable level for Cd in food stuffs?
4. Can input be given to the decision as to whether the exemption for Cd in quantum dots under the RoHS Directive can be scrapped?

These are very specific policy questions that can't be answered by the indicators developed in the course of HBM4EU.

Indicators for cadmium contribute to the general policy questions raised: are there differences in HBM biomarkers for age, sex, ISCED categories? Are there time trends? Are there people at risk?

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9 Conclusions

This additional deliverable provides the framework how to derive HBM indicators and how to interpret them. Furthermore, an overview of the currently available datasets of the selected substances from the HBM4EU repository is given.

Visualisation of indicators was not possible due to the limited available datasets in the HBM4EU repository and the quality aspects that are needed to derive the indicators, discussed in chapter 6.1.

Instead, a framework for the derivation of indicators was developed and the available datasets for each substance group were compiled. The policy questions have also been analysed to see which ones the indicators to be developed could help answer.

Indicators can be drawn when harmonised and quality assured data will become available in 2020 from the aligned studies carried out under work package 8. This harmonised data may allow to generate robust indicators and show if policy actions resulted in minimized internal chemical exposure, if there are inequalities in exposure regarding age, sex, educational level, or between countries, and if internal exposure may have a health relevance.

Based on environmental indicators produced by the EEA, it may also be possible to categorise the indicators in 5 different types in the future:

- Descriptive indicators (Type A) responding to the question: What's happening?
- Performance indicators (Type B): Does it matter? Are we reaching targets?
- Efficiency indicators (Type C): Are we improving?
- Policy effectiveness indicators (Type D): Are the measures working?
- Total welfare indicators (Type E): Are we, on the whole, better off?

For future work, the indicators produced will be analysed taking into account their added value to answer the policy questions gathered in section 7.

Thus, this task will develop science based HBM indicators to directly answer policy questions for better and faster use of scientific results for policy.

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